

Classical Interactions in $dx, dt \rightarrow 0$ Contradicting Special Relativity?

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In a previous note (1), we argued that special relativity introduces two sets of dx, dt intervals, with only one, dx_1, dt_1 , linked to classical Newtonian mechanics. We argued that the second set, dx_2, dt_2 , is associated with 2-slit interference patterns etc. In the case of a photon, the two sets merge. The first set is the Newtonian $dx_1 = v dt_1$ which allows for $dx, dt \rightarrow 0$. The second set is $dx_2 = \text{constant}/p$ and $dt_2 = \text{constant}/E$.

The point we wish to make here is that if E and p , Newtonian variables in the nonrelativistic limit, are really associated with fixed length dt_2 and dx_2 intervals, then this contradicts the notion of interactions occurring in $dx_1, dt_1 \rightarrow 0$, unless dx_2, dt_2 fit inside dx, dt , which are being made arbitrarily small. This can only hold as an approximation, with dx_1, dt_1 taken as tiny compared to system lengths. Newtonian mechanics is associated with changes in E and p , but these are said to occur in $dx_1, dt_1 \rightarrow 0$, whereas these variables are linked with bigger intervals, dx_2, dt_2 .

If, however, dx_2, dt_2 are not small compared to characteristic lengths (times) such as those found in quantum bound problems, then there is a contradiction between dx_2, dt_2 and dx_1, dt_1 and the view of interactions occurring in dx_1, dt_1 need not hold as it doesn't in quantum bound problems.

The problem which arises is that E and p are defined in terms of v in special relativity and v is automatically linked with dx_1, dt_1 for a particle with rest mass, m_0 , but at the same time are closely associated with fixed length dx_2, dt_2 . If E and p are interaction variables and are linked with dx_2, dt_2 (fixed), then it seems that interactions which affect E and p may occur over dx_2, dt_2 (as they do in 2-slit interference). Nevertheless, the notion of v does not disappear and must be associated with dx_1, dt_1 . Thus, it seems that in a bound problem, for which time is removed, various p values are linked with interactions in $dx_2 = \text{constant}/p$, but p is linked with a velocity which is associated with dx_1 and dt_1 . This is fine if one does not consider a force as changing v at a given x, t . Instead, there may exist various p values linked with dx_2 . This suggests a statistical averaging process which would allow dx_1, dt_1 to apply to averaged variables, whereas the averaging process itself utilizes probabilities linked with dx_2, dt_2 .

The question then becomes: What should be averaged and what probability distribution should be used? In a classical bound problem in a time-independent framework, one has a constant E , but $KE(x)$, $v(x)$ and $p(x)$ at each x . We have argued that $v(x)$ must be linked with dx_1 and dt_1 . $v(x)$ follows from both $p(x)$ and $KE(x)$, except in the latter it is $v_{rms}(x)$, thus which should be used to create an average? If $KE(x)$ is used, then $KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E$. If $p(x)$ is used, then $dp_{ave}(x)/dt = -dV/dx$. The interaction variable is p , but it is linked with an interval $dx_2 = \text{constant}/p$ so we use the probability function $\exp(ipx)$ to represent minimal information in space with fixed $\text{constant}/p$ intervals. The problem with dp_{ave}/dt is that:

$dp_{ave}/dt = dp_{ave}(x)/dx \cdot dx/dt$ where $dx/dt = v$ which must be calculated using dx_1, dt_1 mixing

dx_2, dt_2 and dx_1, dt_1 intervals which one does not want with an $\exp(ipx)$ averaging scheme. Instead, one averages over KE and uses v_{rms} .

Special Relativity and Fixed dx, dt Intervals - Effects on Interaction

It is possible to derive a Lorentz transformation matrix for a particle with rest mass m_0 by considering m_0 at t at $x=0$. In a frame moving with $-v$, the particle has velocity $v=x'/t'$ if $x=0, t=0$ transforms to $x'=0, t'=0$, i.e. a matrix transformation is used.

In such a case, the matrix is:

$$\begin{vmatrix} a & g(v/b)v/b \\ b & g(v/b) \end{vmatrix} \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{If this acts on } (x=0, t) \text{ one has: } (x', t') = \{g(v) v t, g(v)t\} \quad ((2))$$

Here b is a constant with units of velocity. The question is: What is b ? One may note that from Newtonian mechanics, one does not only have v appear in $x=vt$, but also in $p=mv$. This suggests that ((1)) may apply to both (x, bt) and (pb, E) vectors. If one wishes to have a magnitude conserved, it cannot be

$$EE + ppbb = momobbbb, \text{ but rather } EE - ppbb = momobbbb \quad ((3))$$

$$\text{In such a case, if } m_0=0, \quad E = pb \quad ((4))$$

Thus, b is some kind of constant velocity associated with a particle with rest mass zero. If one hypothesizes that this is a photon, then b becomes the speed of light in a vacuum which was measured long ago. Two unusual features, however, emerge.

The first was discussed in (1), namely that

$$dx_1 = c dt_1 \quad ((5))$$

, where c is the speed of light in a vacuum. Newtonian mechanics suggests that dx_1 and dt_1 may be made as small as possible. ((4)), however, suggests that there is a second set of measures:

$$dx_2 = \text{constant}/p \text{ and } dt_2 = \text{constant}/E \quad ((6))$$

which also yield the speed of light.

A key point we wish to make is that E, pc , which are considered points in $E-p$ space and exist in dx_1, dt_1 with $dx_1, dt_1 \rightarrow 0$ in Newtonian mechanics, are actually associated with larger fixed spatial and time intervals of ((6)). This is a contradiction of Newtonian mechanics. One cannot imagine an interaction occurring in dx_1, dt_1 which are smaller than ((6)). An interaction in Newtonian mechanics involves E and p and so one must consider physical intervals at least of the order of ((6)). If ((6)) are tiny with respect to characteristic lengths in a problem, then

Newtonian type interactions are fine, otherwise not, as in quantum bound state interactions, 2-slit interactions etc.

One may note that ((3)) holds in any frame so $E' = c p'$ and $E=cp$. In other words, c is the same constant in any frame.

If one considers ((1)) with $a= g(v)$ and $b=vg(v)$, and uses $c=1$, then:

$X1' =g(v) x1+vg t1$ $x2'=gx2+vg t2$ $t1'=vgx1+gt1$ $t2'=gvx2+gt2$ so:

$$\{x2'-x1'\} / \{t2'-t1'\} = \{1+v/v1\} / \{v+1/v1\} \quad ((7))$$

The relation $\Delta x = v1 \Delta t$ only holds in all frames for a special velocity, namely $v1=1$ (i.e. c in units of $c=1$).

Two Sets of Variables

As noted in (1), there are two sets of intervals. The first is $dx1, dt1$ used for $dx1/dt1=v$ which describes movement of a particle. A particle, however, is measured by interactions, including the velocity and so these interactions must occur at $dx2, dt2$ smaller than $dx1, dt1$, but $dx1, dt1$ may be made as small as possible. This suggests that $dx1/dt1=v$ is a mathematical abstraction if one wishes to enforce it via measurements over tiny intervals $dx1, dt1$. One may, on the other hand, use very large intervals and then interpolate, but this then only gives an average view in small length and time intervals.

In Newtonian mechanics both v and interactions are linked with $dx1$ and $dt1 \rightarrow 0$. This can only happen if $\text{constant}/E$ and $\text{constant}/p$ are as small as $dx1$ and $dt1$, but $dx2, dt2$ are fixed and may not be small compared with system lengths and times. Here constant is some fixed constant (which turns out to be \hbar).

As a result, it is the association of E and p , variables of interaction, which are also associated with fixed intervals $dx2, dt2$ which prevent one from having interactions at $dx=0, dt=0$. The question then becomes: How does one describe a Newtonian problem?

$$dp/dt = -dV/dx \quad ((8a)) \quad \text{or} \quad KE(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((8b))$$

If one considers a time-independent problem, then one focuses on $dx2=\hbar/p$. This suggests that space is broken into intervals of this length, but is otherwise uniform. This is mathematically described by the function:

$$\exp(ipx) \quad ((9))$$

((9)) may be used as a probability and one may consider an averaging process. The question then is: Does one use ((8a)) or ((8b)) for averaging? If one uses ((8b)), then velocity emerges as $v_{rms}(x)$ which may then be associated with $dx1/dt1$ as it is a mathematical abstraction as

discussed above, but this occurs only after all averaging has been done with $\exp(ipx)$, i.e. in the dx_2 framework.

If one uses ((8a)), there is a problem because:

$$dpave(x)/dt = dpave/dx \ v = -dV/dx \quad ((10))$$

Here v must a priori be defined by dx_1, dt_1 , but interactions occur in dx_2 which is fixed and there is no need to have dx_1, dt_1 appear in an interaction picture. $v(x)$ and the weights of $\exp(ipx)$ are both unknown in ((10)), whereas only $a(p)$ values are unknown when one creates $KEave(x)$.

Thus, we reject ((10)) and choose instead averaging using ((8b)) with $dx_1/dt_1 = v_{rms}(x)$

Conclusion

In conclusion, Newtonian mechanics introduces one set of intervals dx_1, dt_1 such that both may be made as tiny as possible. These are used not only in the definition of velocity $v = dx_1/dt_1$, but also for interactions which must occur in dx_1, dt_1 and involve E and p . In Newtonian mechanics by itself there is no contradiction.

The problem arises when a second set of intervals dx_2, dt_2 emerge from special relativity. If one considers $EE - ppcc = momocccc$, for $m_0=0$ one has $E=pc$ which means that for E and p in any frame, c , the speed of light, is constant. This equation, as noted in (1), must be equivalent to $dx_1=cdt_1$, but here $dx_2=constant/p$ and $dt_2=constant/E$. These are fixed length intervals which cannot be made as small as possible like dx_1, dt_1 . Thus, the interaction variables E and p are necessarily associated with fixed length dx_2 and dt_2 intervals and so this contradicts Newtonian mechanics unless dx_2 and dt_2 are tiny with respect to characteristic lengths in a system, i.e. fit in dx_1, dt_1 .

If they are not tiny, then interactions in a time-independent picture take place for a given p , over \hbar/p . One cannot have a fixed $KE(x)$ at a $dx_1 \rightarrow 0$. It seems one can only either have $KEave(x)$ or $pave(x)$. In the latter case, one may use $\exp(ipx)$ as an averaging probability (uniform distribution with fixed \hbar/p intervals, $\hbar=1$), or $dpave/dt = -dV/dx \rightarrow dpave(x)/dx \ v = -dV/dx$. In this case, v is linked with dx_1, dt_1 a priori while $pave$, with dx_2 , and so there are mixed intervals which should not be as v is unknown as are the weights of $\exp(ipx)$. Thus, the averaging of $KE(x)$ in $KEave(x) + V(x) = E$ is used.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Energy $\rightarrow \hbar/\delta(t)$ and Momentum $\rightarrow \hbar/\delta(x)$ from $EE = ppc + momocccc$? (preprint, zenodo, 2025)